
FEDERALISM AT CROSSROADS: ASSESSING CENTRALIZATION IN THE INDIAN CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a comprehensive examination of the evolving dynamics of centralization within India's administrative system. Against the backdrop of India's diverse socio-cultural fabric, this paper scrutinizes the delicate balance between central authority and state autonomy. By employing a multidimensional approach encompassing constitutional analysis, legislative review, and judicial scrutiny, the study dissects key constitutional provisions, landmark judicial decisions, and contemporary legislative trends. The analysis reveals a multitude of factors driving centralization, including political exigencies, economic imperatives, and administrative efficiencies. While recognizing the necessity for coordinated governance in a vast and diverse nation like India, the paper underscores the importance of upholding the principles of federalism and safeguarding state autonomy. Centralization trends have far-reaching implications for intergovernmental relations, fiscal federalism, and local governance. The study elucidates the inherent tension between centralized policy-making and the imperative for context-specific governance approaches, particularly in addressing regional disparities. The findings of this study provide valuable insights for scholars, policymakers, and practitioners, advocating for a nuanced approach that balances centralization imperatives with federal principles. A harmonious relationship between centralization and federalism is essential, emphasizing the need for policy interventions that promote cooperative federalism, respect diversity, and foster inclusive development.

Keywords: centralization, federalism, India, intergovernmental relations.

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I. INTRODUCTION

On August 15, 1947, India achieved independence and emerged as a sovereign nation. As stated in Article 1 of the Indian Constitution, India, also known as Bharat, is declared to be a Union of States. Notably, the constitution's framers opted for the term "Union" over "Federation," with the latter conspicuously absent from the constitutional provisions. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar described India as an "indestructible Union of destructible states,"² emphasizing the permanence of the Union despite the states' potential destructibility. Although the Constitution incorporates a federal structure, Dr. Ambedkar highlighted the advantages of using "Union" during the drafting process. This choice implies that India's existence as a unified entity does not stem from a contractual agreement among its constituent states, thereby rejecting their right or ability to secede from the Indian Union.

II. SALIENT FEATURES OF A FEDERAL STATE

A federal state is a political entity characterized by the division of powers between a central government and regional or state governments. Some of the salient features of a federal state include:

1. **Division of Powers:** Power is divided between the central government and the governments of the constituent states or regions. Each level of government has its own sphere of authority, often outlined in a written constitution.
2. **Constitutional Supremacy:** Federal states typically have a written constitution that establishes the framework for governance and delineates the powers of the central and state governments. The constitution is supreme and serves as the highest legal authority.
3. **Autonomy of States:** States in a federal system have a degree of autonomy in managing their internal affairs. They may have their own legislative, executive, and judicial branches responsible for certain aspects of governance.
4. **Dual Government Structure:** Federal states operate with a dual government structure, meaning there are two levels of government: the central or federal government and the state

² K.H. CHELUVARAJU, DR. B. R. AMBEDKAR AND MAKING OF THE CONSTITUTION: A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN FEDERALISM (1991).

or regional governments. Each level has its own set of responsibilities and areas of jurisdiction.

5. **Interstate Relations:** Federal states often have mechanisms for resolving disputes and promoting cooperation between the central government and the states. This may include intergovernmental conferences, councils, or courts.
6. **Equal Representation of States:** In the legislative branch of the federal government, there is usually a provision for equal representation of states alongside proportional representation based on population. This is often seen in a bicameral legislature where one chamber represents states equally (e.g., the U.S. Senate) and another chamber represents population proportionally (e.g., the U.S. House of Representatives).
7. **Flexibility and Adaptability:** Federal systems tend to be flexible and adaptable to diverse cultural, social, and economic conditions within different regions or states. This flexibility allows for experimentation with policies tailored to local needs and preferences.
8. **Complex Governance Dynamics:** Federal systems can sometimes lead to complex governance dynamics, including tensions between the central government and state governments, disagreements over the division of powers, and challenges in coordinating policies and programs across different jurisdictions.

III. CHARACTERISTICS OF A UNITARY STATE

A unitary state is a political system where sovereignty is concentrated in a single, central government, which holds the majority of political power. Here are some key characteristics of a unitary state:

1. **Centralized Power:** In a unitary state, all political authority and decision-making power rest with the central government. Subnational entities, such as regions or provinces, have limited autonomy and derive their powers from the central government.
2. **No Constitutional Division of Powers:** Unlike federal states, unitary states do not have a constitutionally mandated division of powers between the central government and subnational entities. Instead, any powers granted to lower levels of government can be revoked or modified by the central government.

3. **Uniform Laws and Policies:** Unitary states typically have uniform laws and policies that apply throughout the entire territory. The central government establishes laws, regulations, and policies that are uniformly enforced across all regions or provinces.
4. **Single Legal System:** There is usually a single legal system in a unitary state, administered and interpreted by national courts. Subnational entities may have limited authority to enact laws or regulations, but these must conform to the overarching legal framework established by the central government.
5. **Administrative Subdivisions:** While unitary states may have administrative subdivisions (such as regions, provinces, or municipalities), these entities primarily serve administrative purposes rather than exercising significant political power. They are often responsible for implementing policies and programs established by the central government.
6. **Centralized Fiscal Authority:** The central government typically has control over fiscal matters, including taxation, budgeting, and expenditure allocation. Subnational entities may receive funding from the central government, but they have limited fiscal autonomy and rely heavily on central transfers.
7. **Unified Foreign Policy:** Foreign affairs, including diplomacy, international treaties, and defense, are usually managed exclusively by the central government. Subnational entities do not have the authority to conduct independent foreign policy or enter into international agreements.
8. **Greater Political Stability:** Unitary states often exhibit greater political stability compared to federal systems, as there is less potential for conflicts between central and regional authorities over the division of powers or jurisdictional issues.
9. **Easier Governance Coordination:** The centralized nature of unitary states facilitates easier coordination and implementation of government policies and programs across the entire territory. This can lead to more efficient governance and decision-making processes.

Potential for Centralization of Power: While unitary states may provide for efficient governance, there is a risk of centralization of power in the hands of the central government,

which can limit local autonomy and representation. This centralization may also exacerbate regional disparities and grievances.

IV. CONSTITUTIONAL PROVISIONS

The character of the Indian state can be understood by examining the articles outlined in the Indian constitution. The following articles provide insights into the nature of Indian polity.

Article 1 of the Indian Constitution states that India, that is Bharat, shall be a Union of States. The framers of the constitution intentionally refrained from using the term "federation" to clearly convey that India, as a political and administrative entity, is a unified whole, not formed by a pact among states.

Article 2 of the Indian Constitution deals with the admission or establishment of new states within the Indian Union. Parliament is vested with the exclusive authority to admit or establish new states into the Union under terms and conditions it deems fit.

Articles 5-12 grant Parliament plenary powers over citizenship matters in India. Unlike in the US, where citizens can have both federal and state citizenship, India follows a system of single citizenship as per its constitution.

Article 163 (2) strengthens the position of the Governor as an agent of centre in as much as it confers on the Governor the power even to decide if a matter falls within his discretion or not.

Article 280 empowers the President to constitute Finance Commission to distribute the net tax proceedings between the central government and the respective state governments. Here its pertinent to note that the recommendations of the finance Commission are not binding on Central Government

The Parliament shall have (and the legislature of a state shall not have) power to make laws with respect to the following matters:

- (a) Prescribing residence as a condition for certain employments or appointments in a state or union territory or local authority or other authority (Article 16).
- (b) Empowering courts other than the Supreme Court and the high courts to issue directions, orders and writs of all kinds for the enforcement of fundamental rights (Article 32).

(c) Restricting or abrogating the application of Fundamental Rights to members of armed forces, police forces, etc. (Article 33).

(d) Indemnifying any government servant or any other person for any act done during the operation of martial law in any area (Article 34).

Additionally, the Parliament shall have (and the legislature of a state shall not have) powers to make laws for prescribing punishment for those acts that are declared to be offences under the fundamental rights. These include the following:

(a) Untouchability (Article 17).

(b) Traffic in human beings and forced labour (Article 23).

In times of emergency, the Central Government assumes supreme authority, effectively placing the states under its complete control. This transition from a federal to a unitary system occurs without a formal amendment of the Constitution, making it a distinctive aspect of the Indian Constitution.³ Similarly, the Constitution provides provisions for the imposition of President's Rule in a state in case of failure of constitutional machinery.⁴ When President's Rule is imposed, the President assumes state government functions, declares Parliament's control over the state legislature, and can suspend constitutional provisions. The state council of ministers led by the chief minister is dismissed, and state administration is managed by the governor with Parliament passing state bills and budget. However, the state legislative assembly is either kept in suspensive animation or dissolved altogether.

V. MEASURES TO ENSURE HARMONIOUS CENTRE STATE RELATION

From the constitutional provisions it is evident that the Centre enjoys more powers in comparison with State Governments. However, a harmonious relation between the Centre and States is imperative to ensure good governance.

Several Commissions in India have highlighted the need to strengthen the relationship between the central government and state administrations. The Sarkaria Commission of 1983 emphasized bolstering the All-India Services and creating more such services to enhance administrative

³ Article 352 of the Indian Constitution.

⁴ Article 356 of the Indian Constitution.

efficiency. It also advocated for the central government to focus only on areas of concurrent subjects where uniform policy is essential, leaving the rest for state jurisdiction.

The MM Punchhi Commission, convened in 2007, underscored the importance of defining the powers devolved to local bodies for self-governance through constitutional amendments. Additionally, it proposed fixed five-year tenures for Governors and their removal only through impeachment by state Assemblies, mirroring the process for the President's removal by Parliament.

The National Commission to Review the Workings of the Constitution (NCRWC) in 2000 suggested establishing the Inter-State Trade and Commerce Commission as a legislative body under Article 307. It also recommended incorporating emergency and disaster management into the Concurrent List of the Seventh Schedule.

Beyond these commissions, various measures have been proposed to enhance the central-state relationship. Strengthening institutions like the Inter-State Council, Finance Commission, and Niti Aayog is crucial for facilitating cooperation between the Centre and states. Fiscal federalism, promoting equitable resource distribution, and potentially revisiting the seventh schedule to decentralize powers further are also advocated. Moreover, encouraging state-level innovations and ensuring effective power-sharing mechanisms between the Centre and states are seen as vital steps toward fostering a balanced and cooperative governance framework in India.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Union Government in India wields greater authority compared to its provincial counterparts due to the constitutional framework, which differs from a federation formed through state agreements. States are established primarily for efficient administration rather than as autonomous entities. However, it's important to recognize the significant role states play in representing diverse aspirations, transcending linguistic and regional differences. The Indian Constitution's Seventh Schedule precisely outlines the distribution of powers between the Center and the states, preventing any encroachment on each other's jurisdiction. The Indian governance model is built upon maintaining a delicate equilibrium between central and state administrations.